

FROM CONTRACTS TO COLLAPSE – “CORRUPTION KILLS”

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Abstract

Corruption poses a significant threat to the quality, safety, and security of public infrastructure, particularly in developing countries such as Serbia. Based on a qualitative methodology, combining content analysis and secondary data triangulation, the paper aims to examine how corrupt practices infiltrate all phases of infrastructure projects, from planning and procurement to construction and maintenance. Using the 2024 collapse of the canopy at the Novi Sad railway station as a case study, the paper highlights how weak governance, discretionary decision-making, and lack of oversight contribute to systemic failures with deadly consequences. The analysis draws from official documents, investigative reports, and expert assessments to identify institutional shortcomings and patterns of malpractice. The paper concludes that addressing infrastructure corruption in Serbia requires a comprehensive reform agenda that includes full public disclosure of contracts and technical documentation, establishment of independent oversight bodies, and enforcement of accountability mechanisms. It also finds that only systemic reforms, grounded in transparency, integrity, and the rule of law, can prevent similar tragedies and rebuild public trust.

Key words: *corruption, public infrastructure, construction sector, accountability, security*

1. INTRODUCTION

Corruption remains one of the most urgent challenges in global public infrastructure development, especially in developing countries like Serbia. Its widespread influence compromises quality, safety, security, and sustainability, often resulting in catastrophic failures. Corruption in the construction sector has been extensively studied, revealing how practices such as bribery, favouritism, and lack of transparency distort decision-making. These practices weaken institutional capacity, leading to substandard outcomes, safety hazards, and project failures. In Serbia, numerous cases in public procurement and infrastructure projects have raised governance concerns, emphasizing the need for reforms. A tragic example is the collapse of a canopy at the Novi Sad railway station in November 2024, which caused sixteen deaths, highlighting the deadly consequences of unchecked corruption and poor oversight. This research explores how

corruption infiltrates the infrastructure lifecycle, focusing on Serbia, and discusses broader implications for safety, security, economic stability, and sustainable development. The study advocates for reforms to increase transparency, accountability, and institutional resilience to prevent future tragedies.

Methodologically, the study employs qualitative research, combining thematic content analysis and secondary data triangulation. Its aim is to identify governance weaknesses that enabled corruption in the Novi Sad railway reconstruction project. Data sources include academic literature, investigative reports, expert statements, and verified media outputs from 2024–2025. Literature was gathered via Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science using keywords like “corruption”, “infrastructure corruption”, and “Serbia”. Reports from organizations such as the World Bank, the European Commission, OECD, Transparency International, Fiscal Council, and other local agencies were also reviewed. Particular attention was given to documents related to the collapse, including inquiry reports, preliminary findings, expert assessments, legal filings, and official minutes. Credibility, relevance, and accessibility guided document selection, prioritizing official reports over media to ensure reliability. A key limitation is reliance on secondary data, much of which is preliminary or media-reported, which may influence the findings.

The analysis focused on five areas: technical, legal, construction, financial, and media. It looked for signs of corruption, such as rule violations, favouritism, and missing documentation. These indicators, derived from governance and procurement integrity frameworks (Adam & Fazekas, 2023; OECD, 2022; Wells, 2015; Gillanders, 2014), highlight vulnerabilities across all project phases: planning, procurement, construction, and maintenance where discretionary decisions and weak oversight enable corruption. Each indicator was used as a thematic code for cross-comparison of evidence, following established principles of qualitative content analysis. Validation was achieved through triangulation with public reports and peer-reviewed studies, ensuring findings were coherent and empirically grounded. To contextualize these indicators, the study refers to international standards: OECD Infrastructure Governance Indicators (2023), emphasizing strategic planning, transparency, accountability, and internal control; OECD Public Integrity Indicators (2025), focusing on policy coherence and open contracting; and the UNODC Handbook “Towards Building a Road of Integrity” (2023), which frames integrity as a multidimensional process connecting legal frameworks, ethics, and citizen oversight. The study empirically examines how such systemic indicators manifest within Serbia, providing insights into governance weaknesses and the need for comprehensive reforms.

2. CORRUPTION ACROSS THE INFRASTRUCTURE LIFECYCLE

Public infrastructure is widely recognized as a vital driver of economic growth and social welfare. Yet, it has long been identified as one of the sectors most vulnerable to corruption (Schwartz, Fouad, Hansen, & Verdier, 2020; OECD, 2022). Globally, almost half of government fixed capital investment is devoted to infrastructure construction. Many projects continue to suffer from inflated costs, delays, and poor quality. These outcomes are frequently attributed to corrupt practices (Adam & Fazekas, 2023). Empirical surveys consistently rank construction and public works among the most corruption-prone industries (Wells, 2015). OECD (2022) reports that nearly 60% of all foreign bribery incidents occur in extractives, construction, transport, and ICT sectors. This stems from the nature of infrastructure projects large budgets, technical complexity, and multiple stakeholders (OECD, 2022; Adam & Fazekas, 2023). These characteristics create

opportunities for corruption and obscure oversight. In weak governance contexts, officials exercise wide discretion over project selection and contracting. This, combined with poor transparency and low citizen participation, fosters bribery, bid rigging, and patronage (Adam & Fazekas, 2023). Transparency International found construction firms more prone to bribery. Corruption ranges from petty bribes to grand kickback schemes for contracts (Transparency International UK, 2008). Politically connected firms often win contracts via illicit payments, resulting in inflated costs and poor quality. A visible outcome is “white elephant” projects prestige-driven but of questionable value, diverting funds from essential works like maintenance (Pattanayak & Verdugo-Yepes, 2020). These investments often yield negative social returns (Schwartz et al., 2020).

Corruption in infrastructure has severe consequences. Financially, it inflates costs by 5%–20%, sometimes more (Open Government Partnership, 2021). Quality and safety decline when contractors cut corners to finance bribes, often using poor materials or avoiding inspections. In extreme cases, this causes disasters like collapses (Adam & Fazekas, 2023). Corruption also causes delays and misaligns public spending funding new projects over maintenance, worsening deterioration of roads and utilities (Adam & Fazekas, 2023). It wastes resources, endangers safety, and erodes trust in institutions (Varinac & Ninić, 2014; Asuquo et al., 2021).

At each stage of infrastructure development, corruption can arise. In planning, political interference and lobbying often distort priorities (OECD, 2022; Adam & Fazekas, 2023). Companies may bribe to include projects in investment plans. Prestige-driven projects may replace socially valuable ones. Land acquisition and design are also manipulated, sometimes inflated for future kickbacks (OECD, 2022). As a critical point, procurement and tendering see practices like bid rigging, kickbacks, and tailored criteria to favour firms. Other tactics include unjustified negotiations, contract splitting, and overlooking disqualifications (GIACC, 2024). In Eastern Europe, auditors found irregularities in 20% of contract values; single-bid tenders raise additional concerns (European Commission, 2023). In Serbia, over half of public tenders attract only one bid (Open Society Foundation WB, 2025).

Corruption continues during construction fraudulent billing, false invoices, inferior materials, and bribed inspectors. These cause overruns, delays, and safety risks (OECD, 2022; Adam & Fazekas, 2023). Organized crime may worsen this by hijacking subcontracts. Operation and maintenance also suffer politically connected firms secure contracts, toll funds and spare part budgets are embezzled, and nepotism undermines service delivery. Asset disposal or privatization may transfer public assets to cronies at low prices (OECD, 2022).

Academic literature thoroughly analyses these dynamics. Chan and Owusu (2017) classify 28 forms of corruption. De Jong et al. (2009) list 12 types in engineering and construction. Nordin et al. (2011) discuss drivers at individual, institutional, and global levels. Corruption degrades efficiency, fairness, and outcomes. Stifi (2017) emphasizes the hidden and complex nature of corruption in construction. Zarghami (2024) uses a system dynamics model to show how corruption is perpetuated. Its developmental impact is profound, Gillanders (2013) links it to poor quality and inequality; Usman et al. (2009) estimate \$400 billion in annual global losses with major safety concerns. Reform pathways are also discussed. Matthews (2016) finds corruption siphons 10–30% of global construction value, urging joint efforts across sectors. Wells (2015) stresses early attention and institutional safeguards. Collectively, the literature reveals the pervasiveness,

complexity, and consequences of infrastructure corruption and the need for systemic reform.

While international studies confirm global trends, national cases reveal their reality. Serbia illustrates how weak institutions, discretion, and opaque procurement produce a system where politics override expertise. The Novi Sad railway-station tragedy illustrates how theory materializes into fatal real-world consequences.

3. SERBIA'S INFRASTRUCTURE UNDER THE SHADOW OF CORRUPTION

Serbia's infrastructure sector demonstrates how global corruption trends manifest locally, with both high-level graft and everyday malpractices common. One recurring theme is political influence in large projects. During the 2010s, Serbia began partnering with foreign state contractors. Many of these were from China.¹⁷ These partnerships were often established through interstate agreements, which exempted projects from open tender procedures. With the passage of the now-repealed Law on Special Procedures for Linear Infrastructure (2020), the government could declare certain transportation projects of "special importance" and award them directly. This bypassed the standard Public Procurement Law (European Commission, 2023).

Although repealed in 2023 under EU pressure, elements of the law persist. They continue through ad hoc arrangements, such as legislative exemptions for the 2027 World Expo (Transparency Serbia, 2024). Direct contracting, especially for China-funded projects, remains widespread. It continues to fuel concerns about costs and kickbacks. The EU repeatedly criticizes Serbia's non-transparent agreements. It urges open bidding for major projects. Examples of corruption highlight these challenges (European Commission, 2023).

A further notorious incident from another sector is found in telecom. The telecom sector was rocked by a prominent scandal involving Huawei, the Chinese tech giant. This event resembled previous procurement controversies. In 2016, Huawei secured a €150 million contract to upgrade Serbia's telecommunications infrastructure. Leaked documents later revealed the company had paid over \$1 million to offshore firms linked to a senior Telekom Srbija executive. The reason was purported consulting and introductions. Yet experts noted these resembled classic bribery disguised as consultancy fees (Dojčinović & Radojević, 2021). Direct wrongdoing was not proven, but the case highlighted risks in large tech infrastructure procurements. It also suggested telecom contracts, especially those negotiated behind closed doors, may involve personal kickbacks (Dojčinović & Radojević, 2021).

Persistent corruption in Serbia's road construction and public utilities is reflected in repeated procurement fraud and weak contract compliance. Investigative reports uncovered rigged contracts benefiting companies tied to municipal politicians. In 2022, the State Audit Institution found irregularities in nearly 19% of the procurement contracts it examined, reinforcing the view that routine malpractices contribute to systemic risk (European Commission, 2023).

These systemic patterns of corruption within Serbia's infrastructure governance set the stage for the most tragic and emblematic case of institutional failure the 2024 collapse

¹⁷ The first agreement with China in this area was signed in 2009, which was confirmed by the Law on the confirmation of the agreement on economic and technical cooperation in the field of infrastructure.

of the Novi Sad railway station canopy. The event not only exposed weaknesses in procurement, supervision, and accountability but also transformed corruption from an abstract policy issue into a tangible public safety disaster. The following section examines the collapse of the railway station canopy in Novi Sad, an event that resulted in sixteen fatalities and underscored the far-reaching impact of corruption within the infrastructure sector. This tragedy prompted widespread public protests, with students and members of the academic community at the forefront. Among the key messages was a clear and resonant statement: "Corruption kills".

4. CANOPY COLLAPSE IN NOVI SAD – A DEADLY OUTCOME OF CORRUPTION

The collapse of the canopy in Novi Sad is not merely an unfortunate outcome of a construction intervention but also a concerning reflection of deeper systemic issues primarily, the presence of corruption and inefficiency in the reconstruction and maintenance of public facilities. To effectively and clearly present our findings, it is important to further illuminate the environment and context in which the research is conducted, in order to better determine whether and to what extent corruption may be the cause of such tragedies. Our goal is to analyse available data and facts to clarify whether and how corrupt practices have jeopardized citizens' safety, whether it is possible to establish accountability among the actors involved in corrupt processes, and how to create conditions to prevent similar tragedies in the future.

The reconstruction of the Novi Sad railway station took place as part of a major infrastructure project for the planned international railway corridor Budapest – Belgrade – Skopje – Athens and its first phase, the construction of the Budapest – Belgrade railway.¹⁸ The reconstruction of the railway station building was carried out in two phases: the first reconstruction was completed and opened on March 19, 2022, and the second on July 5, 2024. A total of 65 million euros was invested in these works, with 16 million euros allocated specifically for the station building. The reconstruction was carried out by China Railway International and China Communications Construction Company (CCCC) (Gyurkovics, 2024). The contract for the reconstruction work is classified as secret, as the Ministry of Construction, Transport, and Infrastructure of Serbia refused to publish it, citing that "the Chinese partners do not wish to do so " (Kovačević & Prica, 2024).

In the first few days after the collapse of the canopy, government officials claimed that the canopy had not been reconstructed, even though engineers (specializing in construction and geology) illustrated through examples that it had been.¹⁹ The general director of the CIP Traffic Institute, Slaven Tica, stated that "the canopy at the train station

¹⁸ The Belgrade-Budapest railway line is part of the traditional railway corridor connecting Western and Central Europe with Greece, Turkey, and the Middle East. The willingness to reconstruct the Belgrade – Budapest railway has been expressed earlier through The Memorandum of Understanding between the People's Republic of China, Hungary, and Serbia, signed on December 16, 2014. The Memorandum was published in the Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia - International Treaties, no. 1/2015. The works in Serbia are planned in phases, by sections: 1. Belgrade Center – Stara Pazova; 2. Stara Pazova – Novi Sad; 3. Novi Sad – Subotica – state border at Kelebija. The reconstruction of the station in Novi Sad was part of the section Novi Sad – Subotica – state border at Kelebija (The Memorandum of Understanding, 2015).

¹⁹ During the reconstruction, a massive steel structure with heavy glass was added, and the decades-long corrosion of the weights, which could not withstand additional loads, is also highly questionable.

in Novi Sad, which collapsed today, was not the subject of technical documentation for the reconstruction of the station building, and that the complete procedure in terms of design was absolutely followed for the entire building" (Virijević, 2024). The appearance of video footage about the reconstruction of the canopy and expert statements supported by facts led to an admission by government representatives that some form of reconstruction had indeed taken place. Under public pressure and mass protests organized in the meantime, the Government of the Republic of Serbia decided on December 12, 2024, to publish documents from the Ministry of Construction, Transport, and Infrastructure related to the possible commission of a criminal act concerning the collapse of the canopy at the Novi Sad Railway Station on November 1, 2024.

The collapse of the canopy, which caused the tragedy in Novi Sad, raised many questions: the structural integrity of the station, the way the multi-million dollar work was awarded, and the oversight of public infrastructure maintenance. Equally important was the issue of accountability for this tragedy. Although on November 21, 2024, the Higher Public Prosecutor's Office in Novi Sad announced that a total of 12 individuals had been detained and arrested in connection with the tragedy in Novi Sad²⁰, the opposition emphasized that these arrests followed significant public pressure. However, they also stated that the demands have still not been met and that protests continue.

In the meantime, dissatisfied with the work of the state authorities, a group of university professors and experts from various fields formed an Inquiry Committee, which began investigating what had happened during the reconstruction of the Railway Station building in Novi Sad and who is responsible. It was decided that the Committee would operate within four subcommittees: for construction, criminal-legal, economic-financial, and media reporting committee.

The preliminary reports of the mentioned Inquiry Committee and its subcommittees appeared in the media after February 9, 2025, but the final official report was presented to the Serbian public on October 15, 2025 (reports by subcommittees, Radar, October 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21), and the same report was presented to the European Parliament on October 22, 2025. After reviewing the available documentation of the Inquiry Committee and its subcommittees, as well as other accessible sources at our disposal, we arrived at the following conclusions.²¹ First, regarding responsibility, three levels of accountability are indicated: professional responsibility – constructive-architectural deficiencies; legal-formal and criminal responsibility – contracts, annexes to contracts, contractual prices, and responsibility of the highest authorities – enabled, permitted, or ordered the railway station, which still represented a construction site, to be put into use, thereby endangering the lives of people who pass by there daily. Second, the following are the findings in detail:

1. Technical details

According to the findings of all actors involved in the review process of the documentation regarding the reconstruction of the Railway Station in Novi Sad, approximately 21 groups of documents are missing from the documents published by the

²⁰ Including two ministers, the acting director of Infrastructure of Serbian Railways, the former director of Infrastructure of Serbian Railways, and an assistant minister of construction, transport, and infrastructure – sector for railway and intermodal transport.

²¹ Preliminary analysis of the Faculty of Civil Engineering; Reports of the Republic Construction Inspection; Ratings and opinions of associations of architects and independent experts; Additional sources - official records, legal documents, possible applications and appeals.

Government of the Republic of Serbia (including the dynamic plan, monthly progress reports from contractors, documentation related to the selection of subcontractors, etc.) (Dašić, 2025) According to the announcement from the Faculty of Civil Engineering at the University of Belgrade, the following are missing: project documentation (the conceptual design is not available); contractual documentation (contracts and annexes with all subcontractors – incomplete); construction documentation (site reports, construction diaries, construction books, inspection logs, testing and technical documentation, etc.); documentation under the jurisdiction of the investor and documentation under the jurisdiction of the Republic Construction Inspection (Građevinski fakultet, 2025). In addition to the missing documentation, a large number of documents have been published that are not relevant to the Railway Station in Novi Sad but pertain to the entire rail modernization project, which makes the available documentation unsystematic and slows down the process of drawing conclusions.

2. *Criminal legal details*

According to the findings of the legal civil subcommittee, the competent institutions in the executive and legislative branches of the Republic of Serbia are responsible for enacting corrupt and unconstitutional norms that have contributed to the erosion of the rule of law and the creation of criminal structures. Additionally, it remains unclear whether it is economically feasible to use the Railway Station in Novi Sad, given that the responsible institutions have almost not conducted a damage assessment for nearly a year, thereby increasing the overall damage by millions, for which they are directly accountable (Škero&Vodinelić, 2025). It refers to a hierarchically organized corrupt network whose primary objective is the unlawful enrichment of its members. This goal is pursued through the commission of various criminal offenses, including those related to the abuse of official authority (Article 359 of the Criminal Code), economic crimes (Articles 227 and 225 of the Criminal Code), money laundering (Article 245 of the Criminal Code), and violations of the Law on Tax Procedure and Tax Administration (Paunović et al., 2025).²² According to the findings of the legal civil subcommittee there are grounds for suspicion that in the realization of a large infrastructure project, i.e. the construction of a railway from Novi Sad to the border with Hungary, there was an association for the purpose of committing criminal acts in the very top of the country (Paunović et al., 2025). As Professor Marinković states in his authorial text, analysing the work of state authorities, following the collapse of the canopy, the investigation by the Higher Public Prosecutor's Office in Novi Sad has been compromised by controversies related to the expert assessment of the causes of the canopy's collapse. The investigation by the Higher Public Prosecutor's Office in Belgrade is directly aimed at obstructing justice, while the Organized Crime Prosecutor's Office fails to investigate the existence of an organized criminal group, which is suspected to be organized by the President of the Republic and has caused damage to the state amounting to approximately 700 million euros (Marinković, 2025a). The decision of the police director to abolish the Task Force formed by the chief prosecutor of the Public Prosecutor's Office for organized crime speaks of another type of obstruction of the criminal proceedings in this case, all with the aim of preventing the monitoring of money flows, through the financial investigation of all who could be potential suspects (Marinkovic, 2025b). According to Jasmina Paunović, one

²² Note: All findings related to potential criminal liability are based exclusively on publicly available sources and do not imply any judicial determination of guilt.

year after the tragedy in Novi Sad, there is still no criminal proceeding (out of the three that have been started), nor can the main trial be scheduled in the near future (Paunović et al. 2025).

3. *Construction findings*

It was determined that there is a collapse of professionalism at many stages of the analysed project, exemplified by the changes to the Terms of Reference, which underwent several modifications between 2015 and 2023. According to the findings of the Republic Construction Inspection dated two types of violations have been identified: 1. Control and quality checks of all types of works and the application of regulations, standards, and technical norms were not performed (including the lack of verification of the structural stability of the building, use of inadequate materials concrete that was neither approved nor in accordance with technical instructions); 2. Measures to prevent or eliminate immediate danger to life or health of people and safety were not taken (failure to observe occupational safety rules, lack of protective equipment, and the presence of personnel on the construction site whose identity and purpose are unknown) (Republic Construction Inspection, 2024). This indicates a lack of clarity regarding the type of work required on the railway station building, especially the canopy. At the time of signing the Commercial Contract, there was no fulfilled level of project documentation in accordance with the current Law on Planning and Construction, and it was signed when no conceptual design even existed. This reflects the common practice of the current authorities to declare projects worth hundreds of millions or billions of euros as projects of national importance and contract their construction without relevant project documentation (Fiskalni savet, 2024). None of these documents specify or describe the planned works on Wing B of the station building in Novi Sad, particularly not on the canopy. Given that the station building in Novi Sad was constructed in 1964 and there are station buildings on this route that are over 100 years old. It is unacceptable that the Terms of Reference included no comments on the age, condition, or specificities of reconstructing these structures. The building permit covers the entire Novi Sad – Subotica – Kelebija section, including all facilities and equipment, which is unusual given its length of 108 km and the diversity of structures involved. The authorities' goal was to expedite project implementation, often neglecting challenges associated with such a unique approach. Among other things, the building was put into use through an internal procedure (not recognized by law) at the beginning of July 2024, without a technical inspection or the issued occupancy permit. A review of the construction logs reveals a record of the internal acceptance of the building, but the technical inspection of the structure is not mentioned in the logs (Dobrić&Fric, 2025). The contractor independently selected who would control the quality and correctness of the technical documentation he prepared. This directly violates the Commercial Contract and bypasses the public procurement procedures that the investor (Infrastructure of Serbia Railways) and the financier (Ministry of Construction or the Government of Serbia) should have conducted for this service (Kuzmanović&Dašić, 2025).

4. *Financial and economic findings*

The findings in this domain coincide with the previous analysis of the state of investment by the Fiscal Council in 2024, in which they pointed to the growing inefficiency of investment through non-standard procedures (absence of tender procedures), shortened procedures and a large breach of the initially expected price of works (Fiskalni savet, 2024) The construction and reconstruction of the railway

infrastructure from Belgrade to the border with Hungary, including subsequent works and numerous annexes signed in the meantime, has so far cost \$1.33 billion or €1.24 billion. Compared to the estimate by the Ministry of Construction, Transportation, and Infrastructure from 2014, the total costs have increased by €910 million, nearly quadrupling (Dobromirov et al., 2025). The later decision to build the section from Novi Sad to Kelebija for speeds of 200 km/h instead of 160 km/h has neither technical nor economic justification. It is part of the European corridor, which was designed along its entire route for trains with speeds up to 160 km/h, including its extension from the Serbian-Hungarian border to Budapest. Even students at the Faculty of Transport and Communications emphasized that the speed limit was raised to 200 km/h due to political, not professional, will, which unnecessarily increased the cost of the project by 40% (Biznis&Finansije, 2025). Although, according to the Commercial Contract, the Chinese consortium CRIC-CCCC was not allowed to engage more than 54% of subcontractors based in the PRC, they awarded the entire project without public tender to Chinese subcontractor companies CCECC Balkan, CRCC11, CRDC, and CRCEBG and primarily to CCECC Balkan for works on the station building of the railway station in Novi Sad. In January 2022, a consortium that included the French company Egis was selected for supervision, despite the fact that in March 2018, the World Bank imposed sanctions on two subsidiaries of that company one of which was blacklisted, and the other suspended and over the following years, evidence of corrupt activities by this company accumulated (World Bank Group, 2018). In December 2022, President Aleksandar Vučić demanded that the Chinese consortium accelerate works and complete the Novi Sad – Kelebija section of the railway by the end of 2024, approving an additional \$65 million requested by the consortium for this acceleration. Through Annexes 2, 3, and 4, signed by Ministers Goran Vesić and Nebojša Šurlan, the value of works increased by \$86.9 million. Subcontractors, instead of the main contractor, were directly chosen by the Republic of Serbia for "other works". In the meantime, the Public Prosecutor's Office for Organized Crime specified that by concluding the annex, Momirović, Vesić, Dimoski, Šurlan and Katanić enabled the contractor to obtain a property benefit of less than 19 million dollars, as well as that the budget of Serbia was damaged by 115 million dollars (Nedeljnik, 2025). The Chinese consortium, as the main contractor, was not responsible for these subcontractors' work; it only transferred funds drawn from a Chinese bank and the Serbian budget, acting as a conduit, and charged a commission for this service contrary to the loan agreement with the Chinese Exim Bank. Decisions regarding the Commercial Contract and its annexes involved the office of the President of Serbia, the acting director of Infrastructure of Serbia Railways, the relevant ministry, the State Prosecutor's Office, the Ministry of Finance, the Republic Secretariat for Legislation, the competent committee, the Government Secretariat, the Government, and the Prime Minister. The greatest defeat and the most severe consequence of this corrupt activity is the fact that, according to the Infrastructure of Serbia Railways Report from April 2025: "*The construction site for reconstruction, adaptation, and extension of the Station Building in Novi Sad was closed by a decision of the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development (MGSI) on November 2, 2024*" (Kuzmanović&Dašić, 2025). Specifically, when the canopy collapsed, the station building in Novi Sad was an active construction site and should not have been allowed for use. Contrary to that, it was ceremoniously opened twice, and after the canopy was demolished, sixteen lives were lost. This inevitably raises the question: How much is a human life worth in Serbia?

5. *Media reporting*

Most domestic media coverage before and after the collapse of the Novi Sad railway station canopy on November 1, 2024, aligns with their reporting over the past 13 years under the SNS and SPS coalition. In other words, most media outlets serve more to promote government actions than to truthfully, comprehensively, and timely inform citizens. Pro-government outlets prior to the collapse only promoted the government's activities, and afterward, they repeated statements by Aleksandar Vučić, who blamed experts to control the damage an approach that led to the arrest of 13 engineers (Nedeljković&Gavrilović, 2025). Part of the media was in the function of hiding responsibility, diverting attention and labelling those who sought to sanction those responsible. This kind of information and narratives placed by the ruling elite and the president himself did not fulfil the basic human right - the right of citizens to know – which put their lives in question.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, after reviewing relevant literature on corruption in the construction sector and infrastructure projects, we attempted to identify similar findings in domestic projects. We specifically examined the corrupting influence during the reconstruction of the Railway Station and canopy in Novi Sad, analysing decision-making processes, costs, deadline adherence, quality of works, compliance with rules and procedures, and process transparency. We also considered expert opinions and compared them with legal and ethical standards. Deeply rooted corruption practices in Serbia's infrastructure sector from high-level political influence to embezzlement in public procurement not only undermine project transparency and efficiency but also endanger citizens' safety and lives. Serbia has so far failed to fully establish a legal and administrative framework that effectively prevents threats to life, especially by implementing appropriate regulatory measures tailored to activities like construction and reconstruction as hazardous activities, with particular attention to the potential risks to human lives.

Due to all of the above, and as an ongoing process, greater effort is needed to produce clear and precise expert reports highlighting key findings, with an emphasis on compelling evidence of corruption. Only from these findings can recommendations for prevention and elimination of corrupt practices in the future be derived, providing sufficient initial indicators for the relevant authorities, judiciary, and prosecutors to act upon. To prevent similar tragedies in the future, Serbia must adopt comprehensive anti-corruption reforms that integrate transparency, accountability, and professional oversight across all phases of public infrastructure projects. Establishing an independent supervisory body composed of experts from academia, civil society, and professional associations would ensure impartial monitoring and enhance institutional integrity. Moreover, full public disclosure of contracts, annexes, and procurement documents is essential to restore public trust and align Serbia's infrastructure governance with EU transparency and safety standards. Ultimately, combating corruption in construction requires a systemic shift from political discretion to institutional responsibility, grounded in the principles of integrity, openness, and rule of law.²³

²³ An important and motivating factor at this moment is the stance of the European Parliament in "The Resolution on polarization and increased repression in Serbia, one year after the Novi Sad tragedy", adopted on October 22, 2025, which emphasizes that Parliament will mark the anniversary

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